

UDC 477.329.11

**NATIONAL CULTURE IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CHALLENGES
AND CULTURAL INTERACTION OF PEOPLES**

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The article explores the theoretical foundations of the place and role of national culture in the context of global challenges and cultural interaction of peoples, emphasizing its functions as a protective mechanism of identity, a tool of tolerance, and an adaptive resource to counter homogenization through hybrid forms and digitalization. The author analyzes the impact of globalization on traditions as a factor of transformations, the role of culture in economic processes and corporate management, spiritual protection of the individual and deconfliction through patriotic narratives, symbols as amulets, and prospects for integration into the European discourse, offering recommendations for Ukraine's cultural policy focused on sustainability and dialogue.

Key words: national culture, global challenges, cultural interaction, identity, globalization, deconfliction, digitalization, tolerance, hybrid forms, economic integration.

Стаття отримана 9.09. 2025

Стаття прийнята 25.10. 2025

Стаття опублікована 26.12. 2025

UDC 39; 314.15; 316.344.3

**THE TRANSFORMATION OF NATIONAL IDENTITY OF AZERBAIJANI MIGRANTS IN EUROPE
THROUGH THE PRISM OF CONTEMPORARY GLOBAL CHANGES**

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In the era of contemporary global transformations, international migration has become a significant factor influencing the reconstruction of national identities. Globalization, transnational mobility, digitalization, and multicultural social structures have profoundly reshaped the ways in which migrant communities perceive and express their national belonging [2]. In this context, Azerbaijani migrants living in Europe represent an important case for examining the transformation of national identity under modern global conditions. This study aims to analyze the transformation of national identity among Azerbaijani migrants in Europe through the prism of contemporary global changes. The research focuses on key dimensions of identity transformation, including language use, cultural traditions, religious affiliation, social integration, and transnational connections. By examining both first-generation migrants and subsequent generations born or raised in Europe, the study highlights the emergence of hybrid and dual identity models shaped by interactions between homeland heritage and host-society norms [6]. The findings indicate that migration does not lead to the erosion of Azerbaijani national identity but rather to its reconfiguration within a multicultural European context. While first-generation migrants tend to maintain a strong emotional and cultural connection to their homeland, younger generations display a more selective and symbolic attachment to national identity. Language shift, changing family structures, and exposure to European individualistic values contribute to this transformation, while diaspora organizations and digital communication platforms play a crucial role in preserving collective memory and cultural continuity [4], [7]. The study also emphasizes the importance of transnational practices, such as maintaining social, *Introduction.* With the beginning of the twenty-first century, globalization, transnationalism, the rapid development of information technologies, and the intensification of international migration have made it necessary to reconsider the concept of national identity in new contexts [2], [10]. In the modern era, national identity is no longer a static category based solely on ethnic affiliation or historical memory, but rather a dynamic structure that continuously changes under the interaction of social, cultural, political, and economic factors [1], [11]. Migration, in particular, serves as one of the main catalysts in the formation and transformation of both individual and collective identities and directly impacts the social structure of societies [3].

The phenomenon of migration represents not only a geographical relocation but also a process of cultural adaptation, social integration, and identity negotiation. In the new social environment, migrants attempt, on the one hand, to adapt to the normative and institutional frameworks of the host society, while on the other hand they develop various strategies to preserve their national and cultural values. This process leads to the reassessment of national identity and the emergence of multilayered identity models that are often shaped within transnational social fields [5]. Europe functions as a significant social space where migrant identities are

shaped through multicultural social structures, integration policies, and legal-institutional mechanisms [10]. Azerbaijani migrants living in Europe constitute an important social group for scholarly inquiry in this regard. They strive to preserve their national and cultural heritage while adapting to the social values of the societies in which they reside, thereby forming flexible and hybrid identity models [6]. The primary aim of this article is to comprehensively examine, from a theoretical and analytical perspective, the transformation of national identity among Azerbaijani migrants in Europe within the context of contemporary global changes.

Discussion. National identity is a complex concept extensively studied in the social sciences and explained through various theoretical approaches. According to modernist perspectives in contemporary scholarship, national identity is closely linked to processes of state-building, institutional consolidation, and the development of mass education systems, which contribute to cultural standardization and social integration [1], [2]. Within this framework, national identity is associated less with immutable historical continuity and more with the institutional requirements and structural conditions of the modern era.

Other influential approaches conceptualize the nation as a socially constructed and symbolically mediated community, emphasizing that national identity is reproduced through shared language, media discourse, historiography, and collective memory rather than direct personal interaction between all members [1], [11]. From this standpoint, nations are «imagined» not in a fictional sense, but as communities whose cohesion is maintained through symbolic and ideological mechanisms embedded in everyday practices and communication.

Postmodern and constructivist perspectives view national identity not as a fixed or immutable category but as a dynamic structure that continuously transforms in response to social, political, and cultural contexts. From this theoretical standpoint, globalization, migration, and transnationalism weaken rigid national boundaries and enable identities to become more flexible and multilayered [3], [11]. Individuals can simultaneously experience multiple identities – national, ethnic, religious, civic – which become salient depending on the social situation and context. The experiences of Azerbaijani migrants living in Europe clearly illustrate the practical implications of these theoretical approaches. On one hand, migrants attempt to preserve their national affiliation through symbolic and cultural means; on the other hand, they interact with the social norms, legal frameworks, and cultural values of the host societies, thereby reshaping their national identity. This process gives rise to a complex identity model that incorporates both continuity and transformation and can be interpreted through the lens of hybrid and transnational identity formations [6], [9].

Globalization and Migration Processes in Europe. Globalization is characterized by the relative weakening of national borders, the acceleration of capital and labor flows, intensified information exchange, and increased cultural interactions. These processes transform national societies into more open and interdependent social systems [2]. Europe, in particular, represents one of the main regions where globalization operates at an institutional level. Through its unified labor market, freedom of movement, and migration policies, the European Union has created an attractive social space for migrants [10]. Europe also constitutes a complex and multilayered social environment where migrant identities are continuously shaped and reshaped. Multiculturalism, principles of legal equality, and integration policies facilitate migrants' inclusion into social systems while simultaneously enabling the reconstruction of national identities in new contexts. Access to the labor market, socialization within educational institutions, and social welfare systems are among the primary structural factors motivating Azerbaijani migration to Europe [2], [3]. Azerbaijani migrants move to Europe mainly in search of higher education opportunities, economic well-being and family reunification. These forms of migration lead to the redefinition of individuals' social status and the reassessment of national belonging. As they adapt to the normative systems of the host society, migrants must negotiate between preserving their national identity and transforming it in accordance with changing social realities. Consequently, globalization and migration processes in Europe emerge as key structural determinants in reshaping the national identity of Azerbaijani migrants [5], [6].

The Socio-Cultural Profile of Azerbaijani Migrants in Europe. Azerbaijani migrants in Europe cannot be characterized as a homogeneous social group in terms of social, economic, and cultural attributes. They represent various social strata, educational levels, and occupational groups, occupying diverse positions within the labor market and social structures of host societies. Among Azerbaijani migrants are highly qualified professionals, academics, and entrepreneurs, as well as individuals employed in low-skilled sectors. This social diversity directly influences the ways national identity is perceived and expressed, leading to the formation of diverse identity strategies within the same community [6], [9]. First-generation migrants are typically characterized by a strong sense of national belonging. They maintain emotional ties with their country of origin, actively use the national language in daily communication, and place significant importance on preserving cultural values. Memories of the homeland, historical consciousness, and collective past form the core foundations of national identity for this generation. National identity among first-generation migrants often serves a protective and compensatory

function, providing psychological stability and social resilience in the context of migration. It also facilitates the establishment of social networks and solidarity within the community [2]. In contrast, among second- and third-generation Azerbaijani migrants, whose socialization largely occurs within European education systems, media environments, and labor markets, national identity takes a different form. In these generations, national identity becomes more symbolic, selective, and situational rather than embedded in everyday practice. While they preserve certain cultural elements associated with Azerbaijan – such as specific linguistic expressions, national holidays, cuisine, and family values – they also internalize the normative values and civic identities of European societies. This process promotes cultural flexibility and the development of multidirectional identity competencies among younger generations [1], [9]. As a result, a hybrid socio-cultural identity model emerges among second- and third-generation Azerbaijani migrants. This model integrates the social opportunities afforded by European citizenship with cultural memory linked to Azerbaijani origin. Thus, the socio-cultural profile of Azerbaijani migrants in Europe reflects a flexible, multifaceted, and dynamic structure that embodies the transformation of national identity [6], [11]. Language is considered one of the primary markers of national identity and holds particular analytical significance in this context. Among Azerbaijani migrants in Europe, the role of the mother tongue varies across generations. While first-generation migrants actively use the Azerbaijani language in daily communication, its usage among second and third generations is often limited to family contexts and symbolic functions. In many cases, speaking the mother tongue serves less as an indicator of full linguistic proficiency and more as a marker of cultural belonging and emotional attachment [2], [3]. A relative decline in the use of the mother tongue does not imply the complete loss of national identity. On the contrary, language becomes a symbolic component of national identity, performing functions related to cultural recognition and preservation and continuing to occupy an important place in the collective identity of Azerbaijani migrants [1].

Reconstruction of Cultural Values and Traditions. One of the primary characteristics of European societies is the dominance of individualistic value systems. These systems prioritize personal freedom, individual choice, legal equality, and self-realization, significantly influencing family relations, social behavior patterns, and everyday practices among Azerbaijani migrants. In the context of migration, individuals are compelled to establish a new balance between traditional collective values and the normative expectations of European societies. This process goes beyond the mere transmission of national culture and results in its reinterpretation and transformation in accordance with new social and cultural realities [10], [10]. The traditional Azerbaijani family model is based on collective responsibility, internal family hierarchy, parental authority, and close intergenerational relations. In the European context, this model undergoes transformation due to structural and legal frameworks. Gender equality, women's active participation in the labor market, children's early social autonomy, and strengthened individual decision-making reshape the functional structure of family relations. Nevertheless, the family institution remains a key mechanism for preserving national identity and facilitating intergenerational cultural transmission among Azerbaijani migrants [2], [6]. The preservation and reproduction of cultural values are particularly evident through collective rituals. The celebration of Novruz in European countries is not only a continuation of national tradition but also a means of strengthening social solidarity and reaffirming collective identity within the diaspora community. The preservation of national cuisine, family gatherings, and the organization of birthdays, weddings, and funerals with national elements constitute essential forms of cultural self-expression. Through these social practices, individuals symbolically demonstrate their national belonging both within their community and within the broader social environment of host societies [4], [9].

Consequently, the cultural values and traditions of Azerbaijani migrants in Europe are not fully assimilated but are reconstructed and sustained within new social contexts. This reconstruction process ensures the continuity of national identity while revealing its adaptive, flexible, and globally responsive character [11].

Religious Identity and National Belonging. The national identity of Azerbaijanis has historically been shaped through the synthesis of secular principles and the historical-civilizational influence of Islamic culture. The secular state model of Azerbaijani society has framed religious identity not as an essential or defining component of national belonging but rather as a cultural and historical element. This characteristic persists under migration conditions. Among Azerbaijani migrants living in Europe, religious practice tends to be individualized and selective. Religious belief is primarily perceived as a personal spiritual value, exerting indirect influence on social behavior and identity [9]. The secular social systems and religious pluralism prevalent in European countries result in adaptive changes in the religious practices of Azerbaijani migrants. Religious rituals are often confined to specific times and spaces rather than forming part of daily social practice. In this context, religious spaces – particularly mosques and cultural-religious centers – serve not only as places of worship but also as social institutions that facilitate socialization, mutual support, and community solidarity. Accordingly, religious identity functions more as a cultural and symbolic element than as an ideological core of national identity [4].

Transnationalism and Hybrid Identity Models. The concept of transnationalism refers to migrants' simultaneous attachment to multiple social, cultural, and economic spaces and constitutes one of the central analytical frameworks in contemporary migration studies [3], [5]. Azerbaijani migrants in Europe adapt to the legal, social, and economic systems of host societies while maintaining enduring political, cultural, and emotional ties with Azerbaijan. These ties are sustained through family relations, economic transfers, cultural activities, mass media, and especially digital communication technologies [8]. The manifestation of transnational practices in everyday life enables migrants to operate across multiple cultural frameworks simultaneously. While adopting behavior patterns aligned with the normative systems of host societies, migrants also endeavor to preserve national traditions and values within their personal and family lives. This multilayered lifestyle enhances the flexibility of social roles and renders national identity situational in nature [5], [11]. Within this context, a hybrid identity model – often described as European-Azerbaijani – emerges. Hybrid identity allows individuals to internalize multiple cultural codes simultaneously and to emphasize different identity components in varying social settings, thereby facilitating social adaptation. At the same time, this model can generate identity dilemmas, as individuals may experience internal tensions when negotiating which cultural or national affiliation should prevail. Ultimately, transnationalism emerges as a key structural mechanism that enables both the preservation and the flexible, adaptive, and multilayered transformation of national identity among Azerbaijani migrants [3], [8].

Diaspora Organizations and the Preservation of National Identity. Diaspora organizations function as crucial institutional mechanisms for preserving, strengthening, and transmitting national identity among Azerbaijani migrants across generations. Particularly in European countries, these organizations play a significant role in community self-organization, social solidarity, and the maintenance of collective memory [4]. Through diaspora institutions, mother tongue courses are organized, educational activities related to national history and culture are conducted, and national holidays and commemorative days are celebrated collectively. One of the primary functions of diaspora activities is the formal and informal transmission of national identity. Cultural clubs, folklore groups, and educational programs organized for children and youth contribute to the early formation of national identity. At the same time, diaspora organizations serve as intermediaries between the host society and the national community, facilitating the social integration of Azerbaijani migrants. This process ensures that national identity exists not as an isolated structure but as an open and adaptive social construct [9], [11].

Digitalization and the Virtual National Space. In the contemporary era, digitalization has created new opportunities for the preservation and transformation of national identity by forming alternative socialization environments for migrant communities. Social media platforms, online communities, and digital cultural resources enable Azerbaijani migrants to maintain continuous engagement with national culture regardless of physical distance. Through digital communication, national discourses are constructed, collective memory is reproduced, shared, and transmitted across generations, transforming national identity from an individual experience into a collective social phenomenon [7]. The virtual space functions as an alternative social domain in which Azerbaijani migrants can freely express their national identity. Celebrations of national holidays, discussions of historical events, and the sharing of national symbols and cultural attributes on social networking platforms strengthen the sense of national belonging while reinforcing social solidarity within the community. These platforms also serve a transitional function by facilitating migrants' integration into the cultural environment of host societies [7], [11]. Digitalization not only contributes to the preservation of national identity but also enables the emergence of new and flexible identity forms. Since online identities are not constrained by physical space, national identity becomes increasingly globalized and transnational in nature. This process particularly accelerates the selective and symbolic adoption of national identity among younger generations. Consequently, the interaction between diaspora organizations' institutional activities and digital platforms constitutes one of the primary structural mechanisms sustaining the national identity of Azerbaijani migrants in Europe [4], [11].

Conclusion. In the context of contemporary global transformations, the national identity of Azerbaijani migrants in Europe is shaped not as a static and immutable category but as a dynamic and multilayered social construct. Processes of globalization, migration, and transnationalism introduce new dimensions to individuals' understanding of national belonging and necessitate its continuous reassessment. The theoretical and analytical examination conducted in this study demonstrates that migration does not weaken national identity but facilitates its transformation within new social, cultural, and institutional contexts. The multicultural structures of European societies and diverse integration models constitute key factors shaping the identity strategies of Azerbaijani migrants. While migrants strive to preserve their national and cultural heritage, they also adapt to the normative systems of host societies, resulting in hybrid identity formations. This process manifests most clearly across generations: whereas first-generation migrants adopt a more emotional and protective approach to national identity, second- and third-generation migrants exhibit a more symbolic and selective attachment. The research findings indicate that language, cultural values, religious identity, transnational practices, and the activities of diaspora organizations serve as major

determinants in the transformation of national identity. Moreover, digitalization has emerged as an effective alternative platform for preserving and transmitting national identity. Through social media and virtual communities, national discourse is sustained and national identity is reconstructed in alignment with new global realities.

Ultimately, the national identity of Azerbaijani migrants in Europe is not a diminishing phenomenon but a flexible, renewable, and sustainable social entity. A comprehensive understanding of these processes holds significant academic and practical value for shaping Azerbaijan's diaspora policies, cultural strategies, and future research in migration studies.

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УДК 39; 314.15; 316.344.3

ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЯ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ІДЕНТИЧНОСТІ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСЬКИХ МІГРАНТІВ У ЄВРОПІ КРИЗЬ ПРИЗМУ СУЧАСНИХ ГЛОБАЛЬНИХ ЗМІН

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В епоху сучасних глобальних трансформацій міжнародна міграція стала важливим чинником, що впливає на реконструкцію національних ідентичностей. Глобалізація, транснаціональна мобільність, цифровізація та мультикультурні соціальні структури суттєво змінили способи, у які мігрантські спільноти сприймають і виражають свою національну належність. У цьому контексті азербайджанські мігранти, що проживають у Європі, становлять важливий приклад для дослідження трансформації національної ідентичності в умовах сучасних глобальних змін.

Метою цього дослідження є аналіз трансформації національної ідентичності азербайджанських мігрантів у Європі крізь призму сучасних глобальних процесів. Дослідження зосереджене на ключових вимірах трансформації ідентичності, зокрема мовному використанні, культурних традиціях, релігійній належності, соціальній інтеграції та транснаціональних зв'язках. Розглядаючи як мігрантів першого покоління, так і наступні покоління, народжені або виховані в Європі, дослідження висвітлює формування гібридних і подвійних моделей ідентичності, що виникають у результаті взаємодії спадщини батьківщини та норм приймаючого суспільства.

Результати засвідчують, що міграція не призводить до втрати азербайджанської національної ідентичності, а радше сприяє її переосмисленню в умовах мультикультурного європейського середовища. Тоді як мігранти першого покоління, зазвичай, зберігають міцний емоційний і культурний зв'язок із батьківщиною, молодші покоління демонструють більш вибіркове та символічне ставлення до національної ідентичності. Мовні зрушення, зміни в сімейних структурах і вплив європейських індивідуалістичних цінностей сприяють цій трансформації, водночас діаспорні організації та цифрові платформи комунікації відіграють важливу роль у збереженні колективної пам'яті та культурної тяглості. Дослідження також підкреслює значення транснаціональних практик, таких як підтримання соціальних, економічних і культурних зв'язків з Азербайджаном, у збереженні національної ідентичності за межами державних кордонів. Загалом дослідження демонструє, що національна ідентичність азербайджанських мігрантів у Європі є динамічною, багаторівневою та постійно переосмислюваною у відповідь на глобальні процеси й локальні соціокультурні умови. Це дослідження робить внесок у студії міграції та ідентичності, пропонуючи глибше розуміння еволюційних моделей ідентичності азербайджанської діаспори в Європі.

Ключові слова: азербайджанські мігранти, національна ідентичність, глобалізація, Європа, транснаціоналізм, діаспора, культурна трансформація.

Стаття отримана 18.09. 2025

Стаття прийнята 14.10. 2025

Стаття опублікована 26.12. 2025